

Coumarins and Chromones from β -Naphthol.

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The naphtha- α -pyrone derived from β -naphthol and acetoacetic ester yields smoothly and quantitatively an extraordinarily stable coumarinic (*cis*) acid (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 115, 1620, 1630). As far as we are aware, it provides the only exception to the rule that coumarins as a class, and specially those with an alkyl group in the 4-position, offer considerable resistance to the opening of the pyrone ring by alkalis, and eventually form only *unstable* coumarinic acids which cannot be isolated as such, but are reconverted into the original coumarins on acidifying their alkaline solutions. No plausible explanation of the remarkable stability of the methyl- β -naphthacoumarinic acid has yet been offered and there also remains some uncertainty regarding the constitution of the β -naphthapyrone itself (Dey, *loc. cit.* p. 1615). Further work on the constitution of β -naphthapyrones in general has recently been published (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 71).

Bacovescu (*Ber.*, 1910, 43, 1280) first prepared a pyrone which was designated 1-methyl-4:3- β -naphthapyrone (*vide, infra*) having the following constitution,

by condensing β -naphthol and acetoacetic ester with the aid of concentrated sulphuric acid, and the same compound was subsequently prepared (Dey, *loc.cit.* p. 1628) by heating 4:3- β -naphthapyrone-1-acetic acid above its melting point (191°). While preparing large quantities of this pyrone, the curious fact repeatedly came to our notice that although the crude material, after washing free from unchanged β -naphthol by alkali, appeared crystalline and fairly pure, and amounted to as much as 75 per cent of the theoretical yield (16 g. of the uncrystallised body were uniformly obtained

from 14 g. of β -naphthol, the product melted very indefinitely, and the pure β -naphthapyrone (m.p. 179°) ultimately obtained by several recrystallisations of the crude product from boiling alcohol, amounted hardly to 24 per cent (5 g.) of the yield required by theory. The presumption seemed, therefore, to be reasonable that the reaction had led to the formation of some other product or products, the separation of which in a pure state by fractional crystallisation from a suitable solvent or by treatment with alkalis at different temperatures, should be practicable. Attempts at separating the constituents of the mixture by these methods have not yet been successful, but evidence has been obtained from other directions which has settled definitely the nature of the second component. The possibility that the impurity in the present case might consist, at least to some extent, of the corresponding β -naphthachromone derivative suggested itself quite early in the investigation, and a reference to literature showed that the expected methyl- β -naphthachromone, which is designated 3-methyl-1:4- β a-naphthapyrone* having the following constitution

had already been described by several investigators. It appears to have been first synthesised by Schneider and Kunau (*Ber.*, 1921, **54**, 2302) by condensing β -naphthylmethylether with sulphoacetic acid (a mixture of acetic anhydride and sulphuric acid) and treating the resulting 2-acetyl-3-methyl-1:4- β a-naphthapyrone (m.p. 157°) with alcoholic ammonia, when the desired naphthachromone (m.p. 168°) was obtained. Wittig (*Annalen*, 1925, **446**, 155) subsequently prepared the same compound by heating 1-aceto-2-naphthol with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, a mixture of the 2-acetyl derivative (m.p. 157°) and the methyl- β -naphthachromone (m.p. recorded

* There seems to exist some confusion in the method of nomenclature of these bodies. The names β -naphthacoumarin and β -naphthachromone chosen by Bartsch (*Ber.*, 1903, **36**, 1969), Bacovescu (*loc. cit.*), Schneider and Kunau (*loc. cit.*), and others are obviously unsuitable, while the designations 1-methyl-4:3- β -naphthapyrone (Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **115**, 1629) for the coumarin, and 3-methyl-1:4- β a-naphthapyrone (Menon and Venkatesman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, p. 2694) for the

by Wittig is 164°) being obtained. Recently Menon and Venkataraman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, p. 2594) prepared the above mentioned 2-acetyl derivative by the same method as that described by Wittig, and obtained from it the pure β -naphthachromone (m.p. 168°) by deacetylating it with alcoholic ammonia according to the directions given by Schneider and Kunau (*loc. cit.*). The constitution of this methyl- β -naphthachromone would thus appear to have been well established by these syntheses, and the same compound has now been synthesised from β -naphthol and acetoacetic ester by using phosphorus pentoxide as the condensing agent (Simonis' method). The chromone is best characterised by conversion into the 2-styrene derivative which is formed with extreme readiness and separates in almost quantitative yield from alcohol according to the following equation (*cf. Heilbron, Barnes and Morton, J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 2565).

corresponding chromone, do not convey a clear idea of the relationship between the structures of these two bodies. The following system of naming the coumarins and chromones derived from β -naphthol seems to have the advantage of being more consistent and has been adopted by us in the present paper:—

 1:2- β -Naphthapyrone.

 1:4- β -Naphthapyrone.

 1:2- $\beta\beta$ -Naphthopyrone.

 1:4- $\beta\beta$ -Naphthopyrone.

The reaction with benzaldehyde thus affords a suitable test for detection of the chromone even when it occurred in minute quantities, and was therefore applied to the determination of its presence in the crude mixture obtained by the condensation of β -naphthol and acetoacetic ester by means of sulphuric acid. On treating a warm alcoholic solution of the crude material with benzaldehyde followed by the addition of a slight excess of alcoholic sodium ethoxide, considerable quantities of the sparingly soluble styrene (m.p. 198°), identical in all respects with that derived from the chromone, crystallised out in the course of an hour. The pure β -naphtha-1:2-pyrone (m.p. 179°), however, when treated in the same way, gave no sign of reaction or formation of a benzylidene derivative, and on expelling the unchanged benzaldehyde with steam, and acidifying the cold alkaline solution, the stable coumarin acid, mixed with a little unchanged coumarin, slowly separated out.

These results seem to be of particular interest in their bearing on the problem of syntheses of coumarins and chromones by Pechmann's and Simonis' methods respectively. They prove conclusively that coumarins and chromones may *both* be formed under the conditions of Pechmann's reaction in which strong sulphuric acid is used as the condensing agent. This fact does not appear to have been noticed or given due prominence by any of the workers who have recently invaded this field, and it may therefore be not out of place here to dwell briefly on the history of this reaction. Simonis (Petscheck and Simonis, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 2015; Simonis and Lehmann, *Ber.*, 1914, **47**, 697; Simonis and Remmert, *ibid.*, 1914, **47**, 2229) first claimed to have made the observation that chromones and not coumarins were formed when, in the usual Pechmann reaction, concentrated sulphuric acid was replaced by phosphorus pentoxide in dry ether. In a series of papers published by Jacobson and Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, **107**, 425, 959, 1051; Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1915, **109**, 105) the claim was made that chromones had been synthesised even by the use of sulphuric acid. According to these authors the formation of coumarins or chromones in the ordinary Pechmann synthesis seemed to depend on the nature of the β -ketonic ester or the β -diketone molecule, chromone formation being favoured by the substitution of one of the methylene-H atoms by an alkyl or other complex groups. These statements remained unchallenged until Baker and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **127** 1981; Baker, *ibid.*, 1925, **127**, 2349) threw doubt on the authenticity of the so-called chromones synthesised by Jacobson and Ghosh, and

succeeded in proving definitely that the supposed chromones were in reality coumarins. Since then Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 129, 407) and Robertson and others (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, p. 1256, 1877, 2426) have published much valuable data concerning the Simonis reaction and shown that the generalisation made by Simonis is by no means justified, chromones being formed in only a very limited number of cases, *e.g.*, those of phenol itself, catechol, guaiacol, *p*-cresol and quinol, while with other phenols and with α -naphthol, the products were only coumarins. Robertson and others seem to have arrived at the conclusion that while coumarins are exclusively formed by Pechmann's method, the use of phosphorus pentoxides as the condensing agent results, in a few rare instances, in the formation of chromones, the course of the latter condensation being determined by the nature of the phenol rather than by that of the β -ketonic ester employed.

In the light of the observations made with β -naphthol which are now recorded, the conclusion is unavoidable that the proposition of Ghosh and Jacobson, *viz.*, that coumarins and chromones may both be formed in the normal Pechmann process, is fundamentally sound. The important factor which determines the course of the condensation, however, is obviously not the β -ketonic ester but the phenol itself, as suggested by Robertson. It seems to be peculiarly unfortunate that the large number of incorrect observations recorded by Jacobson and Ghosh, the majority of the compounds described by these authors as chromones having now been proved to be the corresponding coumarins, should have misled chemists into doubting the possibility of their fundamental assumption, *viz.*, that chromones are formed even through the agency of sulphuric acid, being correct.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preparation of 4-methyl- β -naphthacoumarin (4-methyl-1:2- β -naphthapyrone) by a slight modification of the experimental conditions given by Bacovescu (loc. cit.).—A mixture of finely powdered β -naphthol (14 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (15 g.) was slowly added to ice-cold concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) and shaken vigorously. After 24 hours, excess of cracked ice was added, and the precipitated gummy mass washed repeatedly with cold water and finally with 20 p.c. methanol when it became granular and easy

to filter. It was then left in contact with $N/2$ -caustic soda for some hours, filtered, washed with water and dried. The pale yellow crystalline solid weighed 16 g. approximately, and melted indefinitely between 125° and 160° . The pure coumarin was obtained by washing the crude material with cold methanol and then crystallising twice from excess of boiling absolute alcohol with the aid of animal charcoal. Colourless plates, m. p. 179° , yield 5 g.

Synthesis of 2-methyl-1:4- β -naphthopyrone from β -naphthol and ethyl acetoacetate.—Powdered β -naphthol (8 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (7.5 g.) were warmed in a flask until a clear solution was obtained, and dry phosphorus pentoxide (15 g.) quickly added and thoroughly mixed. The reaction began almost immediately, but it never became violent and no cooling was found necessary. The mixture was finally heated on the water-bath for 20 minutes, and on cooling, ice-water (200 c.c.) was added, the whole thoroughly stirred and allowed to stand for 2 hours. A dark tar was deposited which, on rubbing repeatedly with N -caustic soda, gradually solidified. It was washed with a little cold methanol, and then crystallised twice from the boiling solvent with animal charcoal. Colourless rectangular plates, m. p. 163° , yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 80.1; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.0; H, 4.76 per cent.). Admixture with the corresponding coumarin (m. p. 179°) depressed its melting point to 140° . The substance dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid to a pale yellow solution which exhibits a bright blue fluorescence (cf. Menon and Venkataraman *loc. cit.*).

2-Styryl-1:4- β -naphthopyrone.—Naphtha- γ -pyrone (2 g.) was dissolved in boiling absolute alcohol (40 c.c. approx.) and the clear hot solution treated successively with benzaldehyde (2 g.) and a solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from 0.5 g. of sodium and 20 c.c. absolute alcohol. The colourless solution immediately turned yellow which gradually changed to an intense red colour. The liquid was refluxed on the water-bath for 15 minutes and allowed to cool when the flask became filled in a short time with a mass of soft yellow needles. One crystallisation from boiling alcohol gives the pure styrene, m.p. 198° , yield, nearly 2 g. (Found: C, 83.9; H, 4.6. $C_{21}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 84.6; H, 4.7 per cent.).

The styrene dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colour and the solution shows a green fluorescence. Alkaline permanganate is decolourised on shaking with an alcoholic solution of the styrene, manganese oxides being precipitated.

The *dibromide*, prepared by dissolving the styrene (0.5 g.) in warm carbon disulphide (40 c.c.), adding a solution of bromine (0.5 g.) in CS_2 (5 c.c.), and shaking for 1 hour, crystallises from hot glacial acetic acid in yellow plates, m.p. 175° (not analysed).

Interaction of 4-methyl-1:2- β -naphthopyrone and benzaldehyde.—An alcoholic solution of the coumarin was treated with benzaldehyde and sodium ethoxide in exactly the same way as that described in the case of the chromone. The solution became bright yellow but did not turn red. Nothing separated even on standing for 2 days. The alcohol was partly driven off, the benzaldehyde removed with steam, and the cold solution acidified. The solid which was precipitated slowly, was found to dissolve only partly in cold sodium bicarbonate. The insoluble portion, on crystallisation from alcohol, melts sharply at 178° , not depressed by admixture with the pure coumarin. The bicarbonate solution, on acidification in the cold, slowly deposited a solid in the crystalline condition. It melts at $143-44^\circ$ with sudden effervescence and the residue which quickly solidified, melts at 178° . It thus proves to be identical with the β -naphthacoumarinic acid (β -2-hydroxy-1-naphthylcrotonic acid), m.p. 146° (described by Dey, *loc. cit.*, 1630).

Condensation of the impure (uncrystallised) coumarin obtained from β -naphthol and ethyl acetoacetate with benzaldehyde.—The same conditions as those employed in the previous cases were observed. The mixture changed colour in precisely the same manner as that noticed with the chromone, and on standing for an hour, the characteristic needles of the styrene separated out almost completely. 4G. of the crude coumarin gave nearly 0.8 g. of the pure styrene derivative, m.p. 198° .

The investigation is in progress.

